

FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA

[Jild: 03 Nashr: 9 (2024)] ISSN: 2992-8915

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

CURRENT ISSUES IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SERVICES

*U. Nosirow*¹

¹ Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of "Library Science", State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan

Abstract: The report discusses the main current issues that modern libraries face in providing information services, as well as possible solutions to these problems.

Keywords: libraries, library and information services, informatization, information, user needs, funding, qualified personnel.

Introduction

Modern library and information services are at the intersection of traditional approaches and innovative technologies. The development of the information society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the growth of digital resources, and changes in user needs require a revision of standard service methods. The informatization of society is radically transforming all areas of life. Information and knowledge have become the main drivers of societal development.

Globalization, which has encompassed all of humanity, is based on communications that elevate connections between people and countries to a new level. This, in turn, influences the increase in the volume of information flows and the accessibility of information resources. The modern library plays an important role in the information space, as it is engaged in the collection, preservation, analytical-synthetic, and bibliographic processing of documents, their systematization, and cataloging. It also aids in navigating the vast flow of information through reference and bibliographic services.

It is necessary to highlight several factors that have influenced the process of information and library services for readers. One of the key factors has been the changing needs of users. Modern library users require not only access to books and printed materials but also to digital resources, multimedia materials, and specialized databases. There is a growing interest in remote services and the ability to quickly access information. Libraries face the challenge of adapting their services to meet these new demands. The solution to this issue lies in the implementation of hybrid service models, which include

both traditional and digital resources, the creation of user-friendly online platforms, and ensuring the availability of library services at any time.

Another factor negatively affecting the process of library and information services is inadequate funding and outdated infrastructure. Many libraries face the issue of insufficient funding, leading to the deterioration of their material and technical base, inability to update collections, and implement new technologies. This limits the libraries' ability to provide quality services. One potential solution is to attract additional funding sources through grants, government support programs, and partnerships with private companies. Active participation in projects aimed at modernizing libraries and improving infrastructure is also essential.

Additionally, it is important to address the issue of a lack of qualified staff. With the advancement of information technologies, librarians need not only basic library education but also knowledge in IT, information management, and skills in working with new digital tools. However, training in this area does not always meet modern requirements. Therefore, continuous professional development for library staff is necessary, including the organization of courses and training on new technologies, as well as developing partnerships with universities to prepare a new generation of specialists.

It is also important to mention the factor of transitioning to digital resources and data preservation issues. This process is accompanied by challenges related to data security, access, and management. There is also the issue of storing and digitizing rare and valuable materials. To address these issues, it is necessary to create and maintain digital archives, develop strategies for preserving electronic data, and collaborate with other institutions for experience sharing and joint problem-solving.

Additionally, one cannot overlook the factor of legal aspects and intellectual property protection. With the increase in digital content, issues related to copyright protection, access management, and compliance with licensing agreements arise. This problem can be addressed by providing legal consultations, developing internal regulations for managing access to information, and training staff and users on copyright basics.

Conclusion

A modern library capable of serving the readers of the information society must represent a zone of creative space with opportunities for free self-expression and creative activities. The library should be equipped with computers and internet access. Library staff must be proficient computer users and be able to design and promote cultural and mass events, as well as conduct individual consultations and exhibitions. Libraries should increasingly transition into virtual spaces, have multifunctional, multimedia websites, and maintain blogs on the internet. Many libraries in the republic are actively implementing virtual and augmented reality technologies, as well as other forms of information technology.

Thus, library and information services in the Republic of Uzbekistan are undergoing deep transformations, during which a number of issues arise that require a comprehensive approach. This approach includes the modernization of infrastructure and staff training, as well as the development of new models for interacting with users. It is important to remember that the library must remain a key link in the education and information system, ensuring access to knowledge for all categories of users.

References:

1. Nosirov, U., Yuldashev, I. Zh. *Library and Information Services: Theory and Practice* / U. Nosirov, I. Zh. Yuldashev. Textbook for Students of the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2023. – p.

2. Mamedova, L. *Libraries in the Information Society: Functions and Role* // Higher Education. — 2015 — No. 2.
3. Mamina, R. I., Pirainen, E. V. *The Role and Significance of the Library in the Modern Information Space* // Bibliosphere. — 2016. — No. 4. pp. 39–45. file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/moluch_240_ch4_Q3klbyv.pdf
4. Tsai, I. K. Problems of integration of publishing houses, bookselling and library and information institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan / I. K. Tsai // Scientific and Technical Libraries. - 2021. - № 12. - p. 57-68. <https://doi.org/10.33186/1027-3689-2021-12-57-68>
5. Tsai, I. K. International cooperation of library and information institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan // Bibliosphere. 2022. № 2. p. 48-55. <https://doi.org/10.20913/1815-3186-2022-2-48-55>
6. Tsai, I. K. Introduction of information technologies in the activities of libraries in Uzbekistan / I. K. Tsai // Bibliosphere. - 2023. - № 1. - p. 39-47. - DOI <https://doi.org/10.20913/1815-3186-2023-1-39-47>
7. Tsai, I. K. Development of the information and library system of Uzbekistan in the context of historical transformations / I. K. Tsai, E. B. Artemyeva // Science, technology and information in libraries (LIBWAY-2019): abstract of the international scientific and practical conference (Irkutsk, September 17-19, 2019). - Novosibirsk, 2019. - p. 213-215.
8. Tsai, I. K. Development of the information and library system of Uzbekistan in the context of historical transformations / I. K. Tsai, E. B. Artemyeva // Proceedings of the GPNTB SB RAS. - 2019. - № 1 (1). - p. 22-25. - DOI [10.20913/2618-7575-2019-1-22-25](https://doi.org/10.20913/2618-7575-2019-1-22-25).
9. Tsai, I. K. Development of library education in the Republic of Uzbekistan / I. K. Tsai // Proceedings of the GPSTB SB RAS. - 2020. - № 2 (6). - p. 63-68. DOI <https://doi.org/10.20913/2618-7515-2020-2-63-68>
10. Tsai, I. K. Advanced training of library staff in the Republic of Uzbekistan as one of the elements of the system of continuing education / I. K. Tsai // Twelfth Makushinskies readings : proceedings of the international scientific conference (Tyumen, May 25-27, 2021). - Novosibirsk, 2021. - p. 426-433. - DOI <https://doi.org/10.20913/2618-6691-12-48>
11. Tsai, I. K. Formation of the mandatory copy system in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Proceedings of the GPSTB SB RAS. 2021, № 2. p. 60-64. DOI <https://doi.org/10.20913/2618-7515-2021-2-60-64>
12. Tsai, I. K. Problems of integration of publishing houses, booksellers and information-library institutions in Uzbekistan / I. K. Tsai // INFOLIB : information-library bulletin. - 2022. - № 1. - C. 24-29. - DOI [10.47267/2181-8207/2022/1-099](https://doi.org/10.47267/2181-8207/2022/1-099)
13. Tsai, I. K. Formation of Uzbekistan's libraries as part of the library system of the USSR / I. K. Tsai // Proceedings of GPNTB SB RAS. - 2023. - № 3 (19). - p. 78-89. DOI <https://doi.org/10.20913/2618-7515-2020-2-63-68>
14. Tsai, I. K. Professional development of library staff in the Republic of Uzbekistan as one of the elements of the system of continuing education / I. K. Tsai // Materialari khalkaro ilmiy conference. - Tashkent. - 2021. - p. 426-434.
15. Tsai, I. K. Features of the development of the discipline “Library and information service: theory and practice in the context of a new approach / I. K. Tsai // O’zbekiston davlat san’at va madaniyat institute. - Tashkent. - 2023. - №4 (27). - p. 87-90

16. Tsai, I. K. Problems of library staff development in the modern activity of library and information institutions / I. K. Tsai // INFOLIB. - Tashkent. - №3. - p. 76-80
17. Tsai, I. K. The role of library and information institutions in the development of intercultural communication of the Republic of Uzbekistan / I. K. Tsai // O'zbekiston davlat san'at va madaniyat institute . - Tashkent. - 2023. - №1 (24). - p. 137-140
18. Tsai, I. K. The influence of intercultural communication on library activity as an open communicative system / I. K. Tsai // Materialary toplami "Yangi Uzbekiston tarrakietida madaniyat va sanatning urni. Tashkent. - 2023. - February 23. - p. 229-234
19. Tsai, I. K. Problems of library staff development in the modern activity of library and information institutions / I. K. Tsai // Proceedings of the conference "Central Asia. Information and library resources in science, education, culture and business". - Tashkent. - 2023. - May 24-26. - p. 343-346
20. Tsai, I. K. Actual problems of professional development of librarians in modern libraries of institutions / I. K. Tsai // Materialary toplami "Madaniyat va sanyat sonasida zamonaviy boshkaruv zharayoni: muammolari va echimlari. - Tashkent. - 2023. - May 3. – p. 217-222
21. Say I. K. Reform of writing in the Context of Socio-Cultural Change and its Impact on Library Activities / И. К. Цай // American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/1802>
22. Tsai, Y. K. The reform of writing in the context of socio-cultural changes and its impact on library activities/ Y. K. Tsai // International scientific-practical conference Integration of science and innovation into scientific understanding of folklore, language and culture». - 2023.- 19 December. - p. 613-619
23. Tsai, I. K. Pedagogical orientation in the activities of information and library institutions/ I. K. Tsai // s6. materials I international research. -practice. conf. The ecosystem of the library sector in the age of digitalization: cooperation, integration and innovation. Tashkent. - 2024. P. 1. - p. 131-137
24. Tsay, J. K. Problems of formation of professional pedagogical competence of future librarian/ J. K. Tsai // Conference materials "Central Asia. Information and library resources in science, education, culture and business» - Tashkent. - 2024. - 15-17 May. - p. 77-82
25. Muminkhodjaeva L.N. Problem-based learning in the holistic process of training specialists at the university of culture // American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education. - 2023. - Volume 01, Issue 10. – P.150-159. - ISSN (E): 2993-2769
26. Муминходжаева Л.Н. Маркетинговые технологии развития библиотечно-информационных учреждений в Интернет пространстве // Моя профессиональная карьера: межд. науч.-практ. электронный журнал. - 2023. - №53. - С.178-185.
27. Муминходжаева Л.Н. Влияние организации самостоятельной работы студентов на оптимизацию изучения специальных дисциплин в кредитно-модульной системе // Madaniyat va san'at sohasida zamonaviy boshqaruv jarayoni: muammolari va yechimlari mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi: materiallari to'plami, 2023-yil 3-may. – Toshkent: IJOD-PRINT, 2023. – С.257-261.
28. Муминходжаева Л.Н. Самостоятельная работа студентов как важный фактор оптимизации изучения специальных дисциплин в кредитно-модульной системе // Интернет и информационно-библиотечные ресурсы в науке, образовании, культуре и бизнесе: материалы

межд. конференции Central Asia – 2023, 24 – 26-Май. – Ташкент: Изд-во НБ Узбекистана им. А.Навои, 2023. – С. 419-421.

29. Савочкин М. П., Гребенюк М. В. Библиотечное образование Узбекистана: прошлое и настоящее //Научные школы. Молодёжь в науке и культуре XXI века. – 2018. – С. 244-247.
30. Гребенюк М. В. Информационные технологии в образовании: взаимодействие педагога с информационно-коммуникационными технологиями и совершенствование информационной компетентности //Информационные технологии. Проблемы и решения. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 36-40.
31. Гребенюк М. В., Савочкин М. П. Активные методы обучения как современный метод повышения качества образования //Система менеджмента качества: опыт и перспективы. – 2020. – №. 9. – С. 127-129.
32. Гребенюк М. Востребованность информационно-библиотечных учреждений и профессии библиотекаря в современном мире //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2020. – №. I (2). – С. 158-162.